

Focality Of Rectangular Planar Butterfly Coils With Square vs. Semicircular Wing Tips: A Numerical Comparison

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ABSTRACT

Advances in neuromagnetic stimulation depend significantly on improved coil designs. Such improvements require a better understanding of the relationships between coil design parameters and electric field distributions. Coils with sharp angulations have been thought to offer improved focality over circular coils. We compute the electric field distribution created by square wing tip rectangular butterfly coils and compare it to the field distribution of circular wing tip butterfly coils. The positive and negative peaks of the electric field of the rectangular butterfly coil are found to have a close spatial relationship to the ends of the central leg of the butterfly coil, a relationship which is lost when circular wing tips are used. We conclude that square wing tip rectangular butterfly coils are better than semicircular wing tip rectangular butterfly coils when distal peripheral nerve stimulation with precise control of the locus of stimulation are desired.

INTRODUCTION

Magnetic stimulation of the human peripheral and central nervous system is a well-accepted neurophysiologic technique. In clinical practice, its utility is weakened by questions about the relationship of the actual locus of neural tissue stimulation to coil geometry. New coil designs to achieve improved focality of stimulation include the planar circular butterfly coil and the planar circular four-leaf coil [1],[6]. Coils with sharp angulations have been thought to offer improved focality over circular coils. Planar rectangular single-loop, butterfly, or four-leaf coils may demonstrate better focality than their circular counterparts. We partially test this hypothesis on a simple butterfly design with a 40 mm long central current path, two 40 mm long return current paths parallel and aligned with the central leg, and four connecting legs either straight and perpendicular to both the central and the return legs (square wing tips), or semicircular convex of diameter equal to the central and return leg spacing (semicircular wing tips).

METHODS

The spatial derivative of the electric field in the longitudinal axis of a nerve is proportional to the transmembrane current [4]. An axon first depolarizes where the negative derivative along the axon of the electric field component in the direction of the axon - $[-\delta E_y/\delta y]$ - is large [3]. This site of

depolarization corresponds to the negative peak of the first spatial derivative of the electric field [2],[5]. The activating function has been defined as the input to the cable equation whose output is the axon's transmembrane potential distribution, and is defined as [4]

$$F_a = -\delta E_y/\delta y \quad \text{EQ 1}$$

where we assume that the axon is oriented parallel to the y-axis. Defining f_a as

$$f_a = \delta/\delta y \int I(y') dy'/|r-r'| \quad \text{EQ 2}$$

it can be shown that

$$F_a = \mu/4\pi d/dt f_a \quad \text{EQ 3}$$

whence it can be seen that analysis of f_a alone suffices to identify the sites and extents of the extrema of the activating function F_a (cathode and anode regions) [7]. Since f_a is a function of the current element intensities and locations only, it can be computed by numerical integration for any arbitrary coil geometry and configuration. In this work, we take a contemporary coil design, the butterfly coil, simplify its geometry and the associated field calculations by making it rectangular (hence the name square wing tip butterfly coil), and compute its field distribution. We then repeat the calculation after modifying the wing tips from square to semicircular. A 100*100 rectangular computational grid is used. Butterfly coil wings are 22.5 mm wide and 40 mm high. The center limb of the coil carries the total current $2*I$. Each return limb carries a current I . Only current elements or element projections parallel to the y-axis will contribute to f_a . Integration along the 40 mm long y-directed current paths is done by summation on 8 segments of 5 mm each. Integration along the semicircular wing tips is done by summation on 7 segments of 5.03 mm each. All computations and plots are performed on a PC-clone (486DX2-66) with a commercial numerical package (MATH-CAD)

RESULTS

Contour plots of the modified activating function f_a for the butterfly coils with square wing tips (BC-SW) and with semicircular wing tips (BC-CW) are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively. For BC-SW, the separation of virtual cathode and anode is found to be 46.8 mm, whereas for BC-CW, the separation is found to be 59.6 mm. Compared to the tip of the 40 mm long central leg of the coil, the virtual cathode is offset by 3.4 mm in the BC-SW design and by 9.8

mm in the BC-CW.

DISCUSSION

While magnetic stimulation is a well accepted neurophysiologic technique for both the central and peripheral nervous system, one of its major criticisms remains the poor understanding of the precise relation of coil geometry to the site of nervous tissue excitation. Advances are therefore desirable both in developing numerical techniques to compute and plot the fields associated with current coil designs, and in developing new coil geometries with improved focality. Our results allow direct comparison of two different implementations of a coil design parameter, i.e. the shape of the return current path between the central and peripheral legs of a rectangular butterfly coil. Comparison of the results suggests that the square wing tip butterfly coil offers closer association between coil geometry and computed site of nerve stimulation than the corresponding semicircular wing tip design. An operator performing nerve conduction studies who assumes that the locus of nerve stimulation lies exactly underneath the tip of the central leg of the butterfly coil described above would incur latency errors of 0.068 ms with BC-SW and 0.196 ms with BC-CW, assuming a nerve conduction velocity of 50 m/s.

CONCLUSION

In neuromagnetic stimulation, the introduction of 90 degree angulations in coil geometries allows improved control and understanding of the locus of nerve stimulation.

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Fig. 1 Modified activating function f_a for the square wing tip rectangular butterfly coil

Fig. 2 Modified activating function f_a for the semicircular wing tip rectangular butterfly coil